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Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
DUTASTERIOD & TAMSULOSIN BY USING RP- HPLC****Vinay Kumar Nema*, Chaitanya Bangari, Chandaka Madhu,
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Article Received: March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

The method development and validation of Dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride was done by RP-HPLC with the mobile phase was Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 80:20 % v/v. A Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μm, Make XTerra) column used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 274 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. the linearity range of Dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride were found to be from 25-125 mg/ml. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999. The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 97-102% of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride LOD and LOQ was found to be within limit. There was a significant degradation in the presence of 0.1N HCl, 0.1N NaOH, 3% H2O2 and also on heat. C18 column guarantees better peak shape, better resolution and lower pressure during operation. So the method is stability indicating.

Keywords: Dutasteride, Tamsulosin Hydrochloride, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Degradation, Stability.**Corresponding author:****Vinay Kumar Nema,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Analytical chemistry is the study of the separation, identification, and quantification of the organic components of natural and artificial materials. It deals with mainly Qualitative Method and Quantitative Method [1].

Dutasteride is an white coloured powder which was soluble in ethanol, methanol, and polyethylene glycol but it was insoluble in water. It was Store at 25°C and which was a competitive and specific inhibitor of both type 1 and 2.5 alpha-reductase isoenzymes.

Tamsulosin is an white crystalline coloured powder which was sparingly soluble in water and methanol, slightly soluble in glacial acetic acid and ethanol, and practically insoluble in ether. It was store at 25°C and which was an selective antagonist at alpha-1A and alpha-1B-adrenoceptors in the prostate, prostatic capsule, prostatic urethra, and bladder neck [2].

Present study aims to develop simple, rapid, greater sensitivity and faster elution by using RP-HPLC for the simultaneous estimation of dutasteride and tamsulosin. The developed RP-HPLC method was applied for the forced degradation studies and the method was validated for its parameters as per ICH guidelines.

OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS:

Temperature	:	Ambient
Column	:	Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm,
Make	:	XTerra) or equivalent
Buffer	:	7.0 grams of potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate in 1000 ml water pH adjusted with ortho phasparic acid.
pH	:	2.5
Mobile phase	:	phosphate Buffer: acetonitrile (20: 80 v/v)
Flow rate	:	0.8 ml per min
Wavelength	:	274 nm
Injection volume	:	20 µl
Run time	:	7min.

Optimized chromatogram is shown in the Figure 1(a) and blank is shown in the Fig 1(b). System suitability parameters are shown in Figure 2 results are shown in Table 1

Preparation of mobile phase:

Validation Parameters [9-20]

Precision:

- Standard Solution Preparation

Accurately weighed amount of 50mg Dutasteride (DUT) and 50 mg Tamsulosin (TAM) were taken to a 100 ml clean and dry volumetric flask. This was then

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY:**Method Development [3-8]**

Mobile phase optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was methanol: Ammonium acetate buffer and acetonitrile: phosphate buffer with various combinations of pH as well as varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to potassium dihydrogen phosphate with buffer (pH 2.5), acetonitrile in proportion 20: 80 V/V respectively.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of 10 µg / ml dutasteride and tamsulosin in diluents was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum, the wavelength of 274 nm was selected. At this wavelength dutasteride and tamsulosin standards shows good absorbance.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various columns like hypersil column, lichrosorb, and inertsil ODS column. C18 column of XTerra (150mm x 4.6) was found to be ideal as it gave a good peak shape and resolution at 0.8ml/min flow.

Accurately measured 200 ml (20%) of above buffer and 800 ml of Acetonitrile HPLC (80%) were mixed and degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration. This was used as diluent.

diluted with 70 ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 100 ml with the same solvent. This was taken as stock solution. Further, 1.5 ml of above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with the diluent to get final concentration of 75µg/ml.

- Sample Solution Preparation

Weight equivalent to 50 mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride sample were weighed this was taken into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask and about 70ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and volume made up to the mark with the same solvent. This was taken as stock solution. Further, 1.5 ml of above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent to get final concentration of 75µg/ml.

The standard and sample solutions of 75 µg/ml was injected five times and the peak areas were recorded as shown in Figure 3.1 (a) - 3.1 (e)

The mean and percentage relative standard deviation were calculated from the peak areas and shown in the Table 2 and 3.

Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness

- 75 µg/ml of the above sample solution was injected five times in five different days and peak areas were recorded.

Chromatograms were recorded as shown in Figure 3.2 (a)- 3.2(e) and results are shown in Table 4 and 5.

ACCURACY:

For accuracy determination, three different concentrations were prepared separately i.e. 50%, 100% and 150% for the analyte and chromatograms are recorded for the same.

The chromatograms were recorded as shown in Figure 3.3 (a) – 3.3 (c) and results are shown in Table 6. The % Assay was calculated using the following formula

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{\frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{DS} \times \frac{DT}{WT} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. Wt}}{\text{Label Claim}} \times 100}{1}$$

Where:

- AT = average area counts of sample preparation.
- AS = average area counts of standard preparation.
- WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg.
- P = Percentage purity of working standard

LINEARITY:

For determination of linearity five different concentrations i.e. 25%, 50%, 100%, 125%, 150% were prepared and chromatograms are recorded for same.

- Preparation of sample stock solution
Weight equivalent to 50 mg of sample was weighed in to 100ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same diluent (500 µg/ml).
Preparation of 25% solution (25µg/ml)
0.5ml of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with the diluent.
Preparation of 50% solution (50µg/ml)

Preparation of Sample solutions

Preparation of 50% solution (37.5 µg/ml).

About 25mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin were weighed and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. Further 1.5 ml of above solution was diluted to 10ml with the diluent to get 37.5µg/ml.

Preparation of 100% solution (75 µg/ml)

About 50mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin were weighed and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. Further 1.5 ml of above solution was diluted to 10ml with the diluent to get 75µg/ml.

Preparation of 150% solution (112.5 µg/ml)

About 75mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin were weighed and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. Further 1.5 ml of above solution was diluted to 10ml with the diluent to get 112.5µg/ml.

These solutions were filtered through 0.45µ membrane and stored. Each solution was injected three times under optimized conditions.

1.0ml of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with the diluent.

Preparation of 100% solution (75µg/ml)

1.5ml of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with the diluent.

Preparation of 125% solution (100µg/ml)

2.0ml of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with the diluent.

Preparation 150% solution (125µg/ml)

2.5ml of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with the diluent.

10µl of each 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%, and 125% were injected in triplicate and recorded the peak response.

The chromatograms were recorded as show in Figure 3.4 (a) – 3.4 (e) and results are shown in Table- 7 and 8.

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD)

Limit of detection is the lowest concentration of the substance that can be detected, not necessarily quantified by the method. (Regression statistics)

The minimum concentration at which the analyte can be detected is determined from the linearity curve by applying the following formula.

$$\text{Limit of detection (LOD)} = \frac{\sigma}{S} \times 3.3$$

Where S – slope of the calibration curve

σ – Residual standard deviation

The chromatograms were recorded as show in Figure 3.5 (a) and 3.5 (b) and results are shown in Table- 9

LIMIT OF QUANTITATION (LOQ)

Limit of quantitation is the lowest concentration of the substance that can be estimated quantitatively. It can be determined from linearity curve by applying the following formula

$$\text{Limit of quantitation (LOQ)} = \frac{\sigma}{S} \times 10$$

Where S – slope of the calibration curve

σ – Residual standard deviation

The chromatograms were recorded as show in Figure 3.6 (a) and 3.6 (b) and results are shown in Table- 10

ROBUSTNESS

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results.

Preparation of sample solution (75 μ g/ml)

About 50mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin were weighed and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. Further 1.5 ml of above solution was diluted to 10ml with the diluent to get 75 μ g/ml.

Effect of Variation of flow

The sample was analyzed at 0.7 ml/min and 0.9 ml/min instead of 0.8 ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected twice and chromatograms were recorded.

Effect of Variation of mobile phase organic composition

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. phosphate buffer: acetonitrile was taken in the ratio 15: 85 v/v and 25:75 v/v instead of 20:80 v/v, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected twice and chromatograms were recorded.

The chromatograms were recorded as shown in Figure 3.7 (a) - 3.7 (d) and results are shown in Table 11 and 12.

STABILITY STUDIES:

Acid degradation

Accurately weighed and transferred 10mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride working standard into a 10ml volumetric flask added about 3 ml of 0.1N HCl and sonicated for 10minutes and kept it in darkness for 24 hours then refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hours. After one hour the sample solution was neutralized using 0.1N NaOH and diluted up to the mark with diluent. This was taken as stock solution.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter. This solution was injected and analysed. Peak response was measured.

Alkaline Degradation

Accurately weighed and transferred 10mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride working standard into a 10ml volumetric flask .About 3ml of 0.1N NaOH was added and sonicated for 10minutes kept in darkness for 24 hours and refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour. After one hour the sample solution was neutralized using 0.1N HCl and diluted up to the mark with diluents. This was taken as stock solution.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter. This solution was injected and analysed. Peak response was measured.

Thermal Degradation

Accurately weighed and transferred 10mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride working standard into a 10ml volumetric flask and kept in oven under heat at 105 degrees for 24 hours. This was taken as stock solution.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through

0.45 μ m filter. This solution was injected and analysed. Peak response was measured.
Peroxide Degradation

Accurately weighed and transferred 10mg of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride working standard into a 10ml volumetric flask added about 3ml of 3% Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) and sonicated for 10 minutes and kept in darkness for 12 hours and refluxed

under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hours.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter. This solution was injected and analysed. Peak response was measured.

Chromatograms were recorded as shown in the Figure 4.1 – 4.4 and results are shown in Table 13.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized chromatogram is obtained by following conditions

Figure no 1(a) Chromatogram for dutasteride and tamsulosin

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the dutasteride and tamsulosin peaks are well separated
Retention time of dutasteride – 2.003 min
Retention time of tamsulosin - 5.067 min.

Figure 1(b) Chromatogram for blank

From the above chromatogram it was observed that there are no interferences

System suitability:

The system suitability of the method was checked by injecting five different preparations of the dutasteride and tamsulosin standard. The parameters of system suitability were checked.

Figure 2 Chromatogram for system suitability

Table 1 Results of system suitability parameters for dutasteride and tamsulosin

S. No	Name	Retention time(min)	Area (μ V sec)	Height (μ V)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Dutasteride	2.003	920101	116666		1.6	2711.8
2	Tamsulosin	5.067	552058	41531	11.0	1.3	3428.2

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs should not be less than 2
- Theoretical plates should not be less than 2000
- Tailing factor should not be less than 0.9 and not more than 2.

It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

Validation parameters:

Precision:

Precision of the method was carried out for both sample and standard solutions as described under experimental work. The corresponding chromatograms and results are shown below.

Method precision:

Figure no 3.1 (a) Chromatogram for sample injection -1

Figure no 3.1(b) Chromatogram for sample injection-2

Figure no 3.1 (c) Chromatogram for sample injection-3

Figure no 3.1 (d) Chromatogram for sample injection-4

Figure no 3.1 (e) Chromatogram for sample injection-5

TABLE 2 Results of method precision for Dutasteride:

S. No	Sample area	Standard area	Percentage purity
1	983375	971536	101.04
2	985049	973007	101.03
3	982956	975717	100.54
4	985219	978909	100.44
5	994145	981422	101.09
Average			100.84
%RSD			0.304

TABLE 3 Results of method precision for Tamsulosin

S. No	Sample area	Standard area	Percentage purity
1	592403	577531	101.36
2	592352	580381	101.85
3	592357	577723	102.32
4	592323	582190	101.44
5	596525	583378	101.09
Average			101.24
%RSD			0.46

Acceptance criteria:

%RSD for sample should be NMT 2

- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 2, which is within the limits hence the method is precise.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION (ruggedness):

There was no significant change in assay content and system suitability parameters at different conditions of ruggedness like day to day and system to system variation.

Figure 3.1 (f) Chromatogram for sample injection-1

Figure 3.1 (g) Chromatogram for sample injection-2

Figure 3.1 (h) Chromatogram for sample injection-3

Figure 3.1 (i) Chromatogram for sample injection-4

Figure 3.2 (j) Chromatogram for sample injection-5

Table 4 Results of Intermediate precision for Dutasteride

S. No	Sample area	Standard area	Percentage purity
1	979556	984395	99.30
2	982467	984039	99.64
3	979717	983976	99.36
4	978909	984278	99.28
5	981432	973915	100.57
Average			99.63
%RSD			0.54

Table 5 Results of Intermediate precision for tamsulosin

S. No	Sample area	Standard area	Percentage purity
1	583416	593403	99.12
2	583657	594352	99.01
3	584731	593357	99.52
4	583594	592673	99.61
5	597649	593671	99.12
Average			99.27
%RSD			0.27

Acceptance criteria:

%RSD of five different sample solutions should not be more than 2

- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

ACCURACY:

Sample solutions at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) were prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Figure no 3.3 (a) Chromatogram for sample concentration-50%

Figure no 3.3 (b) Chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

Figure no 3.3 (c) Chromatogram for sample concentration-150%

Table 6 Results of Accuracy

Sample concentration	Sample set no	Sample area		Assay		% Recovery	
		DUT	TAM	DUT	TAM	DUT	TAM
50%	1	460064	276931	24.9	25.0	99.8	100
	2	460124	276694	24.6	24.9	99.6	99.6
	3	460216	276891	24.8	24.9	99.8	99.6
	Average Recovery					99.7%	99.7%
100%	1	923429	554156	49.9	50.0	99.8	100
	2	923654	554897	49.8	49.9	99.6	99.8
	3	923742	556371	49.8	49.9	99.6	99.8
	Average recovery					99.6%	99.8%
150%	1	1387901	828113	74.8	75.0	99.8	100
	2	1385360	828794	74.9	74.9	99.8	99.8
	3	1386984	828349	74.6	74.8	99.6	99.8
	Average recovery					99.7%	99.8%

Acceptance criteria:

The percentage recovery at each level should be between (97-103%).

- The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence the method is accurate.

Linearity:

The linearity range was found to lie from 25% to 125% and chromatograms are shown below.

Figure no 3.4 (a) Chromatogram for linearity concentration-25%

Figure no 3.4 (b) Chromatogram for linearity concentration-50%

Figure no 3.4 (c) Chromatogram for linearity concentration-75%

Figure no 3.4 (d) Chromatogram for linearity concentration-100%

Figure no 3.4 (e) Chromatogram for linearity concentration-125%

Table 7 Area of different concentration of dutasteride and tamsulosin

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area of Dutasteride	Peak area of Tamsulosin
25	296800	179891
50	653819	387781
75	983775	599708
100	1342535	799619
125	1694286	1019614

Figure 3.4 (f) Calibration graph for dutasteride at 274 nm Figure 3.4 (g) Calibration graph for tamsulosin at 274 nm

Table 8 Analytical performance parameters of dutasteride and tamsulosin

Parameters	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin
Slope (m)	13644	8192
Intercept (c)	24221	14308
Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.999	0.999

Acceptance criteria:

Correlation coefficient (R²) should not be less than 0.999

- The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 which is in the acceptance limit. The linearity was established in the range of 25 to 150µg/ml.

LIMIT OF DETECTION FOR DUTASTERIDE AND TAMSULOSIN

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

(a) Chromatogram of dutasteride showing LOD

Figure no 3.5 (b) Chromatogram of tamsulosin showing LOD

Table 9 Results of LOD

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Dutasteride	56	176	3.14
Tamsulosin	56	154	2.75

Acceptance criteria:

Signal to noise ratio should be 3 for LOD solution

- The results obtained are within the limit.

Limit of quantitation for dutasteride and tamsulosin:

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

Figure no 3.6 (a) Chromatogram of dutasteride showing LOQ

Figure no 3.6 (b) Chromatogram of tamsulosin showing LOQ

Table 10 results of LOQ

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Dutasteride	56	563	10.05
Tamsulosin	56	558	9.96

Acceptance criteria:

Signal to noise ratio should be 10 for LOQ solution

- The results obtained are within the limit.

Robustness:

The standard and samples of dutasteride and tamsulosin were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count. Variation in flow

Figure no 3.7 (a) Chromatogram showing less flow of 0.7ml/min

Figure no 3.7 (b) Chromatogram showing more flow of 0.9ml/min

Variation of mobile phase composition

Figure no 3.7 (c) Chromatogram showing less organic composition

Figure no 3.7 (d) Chromatogram showing more organic composition

Table 11 Results for effect of variation in flow

S. No	peak area for Less flow (0.7 ml/min)		peak area for More flow (0.9 ml/min)	
	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin
1	983465	575351	971563	592641
2	985134	580381	973021	592352
3	983467	587724	975674	595471
4	985217	583190	978974	594416
5	994245	584468	984542	583453
Mean	986306	582223	976755	591667
%RSD	0.45	0.80	0.53	0.80

Table 12 Results for effect of variation in mobile phase composition

S. No	peak area for Less organic(70%)		Peak area for More organic (90%)	
	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin
1	984565	574371	981565	593761
2	986134	585481	983527	592462
3	984268	587627	985489	594491
4	986216	585362	987954	596316
5	995247	585448	994672	587353
Mean	987286	583658	986641	592877
%RSD	0.45	0.90	0.51	0.57

Acceptance criteria:

Percentage RSD should not be more than 2.

- The %RSD obtained for change of flow rate, variation in mobile phase was found to be below 2, which is within the acceptance criteria. Hence the method is robust.

Stability indicating studies:

Acid degradation

Degradation was observed by the addition of 0.1 N HCl

Figure 4.1 Chromatogram of acid degradation study

Alkaline degradation

Degradation was observed by the addition of 0.1 N NaOH

Figure 4.2 Chromatogram of alkaline degradation study

Thermal degradation

Degradation was observed when the sample solution was kept under heat at 105⁰ C for 24 hours.

Figure 4.3 Chromatogram of thermal degradation study

Peroxide degradation

Degradation was observed by the addition of 3% H₂O₂

Figure 4.4 Chromatogram of peroxide degradation study

Table 13 Results for degradation studies of dutasteride and tamsulosin

S. no	Type of degradation	Weight of sample (ppm)	Area of sample		Assay content (% w/w)	
			Duta	Tam	Duta	Tam
1	Acid (0.1N HCl)	75	848682	505192	91.87	91.37
2	Base (0.1N NaOH)	75	830431	494327	89.89	89.41
3	Peroxide (3% H ₂ O ₂)	75	784529	439981	84.92	79.58
4	Thermal (at 105°C)	75	793929	472599	85.94	85.48

The degradation was observed slightly in HCl, NaOH, H₂O₂, and also in thermal.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

On the basis of experimental results, the proposed method is suitable for the quantitative determination of dutasteride and tamsulosin in pharmaceutical dosage form, as well as stability testing. Degradation studies were carried out to know the stability indicating capacity to the method. The method provides great sensitivity, adequate linearity and repeatability.

The estimation of Dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was pH 2.5 and the mobile phase was optimized which consists of Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 80:20 % v/ v. A Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm, Make XTerra) column used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 274 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. the linearity range of Dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride were found to be from 25-125 µg/ml. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999.

The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 97-102% of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride LOD and LOQ was found to be within limit.

There was a significant degradation in the presence of 0.1N HCl, 0.1N NaOH, 3% H₂O₂ and also on heat. C18 column guarantees better peak shape, better resolution and lower pressure during operation. So the method is stability indicating. The proposed method is precise, simple and accurate to determine the amount of dutasteride and tamsulosin in formulation.

High percentage of recovery shows that the method is free from the interference of excipients used in the formulation. So the method can be useful in the routine quality control of these drugs.

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